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PROCEEDINGS

TwinSubDyn Summer School

on Sustainable organic amendment applications from a soil
and ground water management perspective
-learning, training, and knowledge exchange activity-

02-06. June 2025, Novi Sad, Serbia

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Event summary

The Summer School is organized as part of the horizon Europe TwinSubDyn project. Summer School, designed to provide a deep dive into the transformative effects of organic soil amendments on soil organic carbon, nutrient dynamics, and contaminant behavior in the soil subsurface, with profound implications for groundwater quality. This comprehensive program offers participants a unique blend of theoretical lectures and hands-on demonstrations, guided by leading experts in the field. Key Objectives: (1) Explore the intricate relationships between organic soil amendments and soil quality, focusing on carbon sequestration, nutrient cycling, and contaminant mitigation in the subsurface environment. (2) Provide attendees with practical insights and methodologies for implementing organic soil amendments to address soil and groundwater challenges effectively. (3) Foster a collaborative environment for knowledge exchange and networking among participants and experts in soil science and environmental remediation. (4) Empower early-stage researchers with essential soft skills training, including experimental design, statistical analysis, scientific writing, and navigating the landscape of ESR career development, targeting appropriate calls to participate in and how to do impactful research. During the summer school, participants will have the chance to showcase their work in their respective fields through abstract submission, and oral presentations or poster sessions.

Topics of interest

1. Long term stability of organic soil amendment,
2. Nutrient management of organic soil amendments;
3. Carbonising sewage sludge or biosolids to remove pollutants;
4. Fate and transport of emerging pollutants in organic soil amendments,

General training topics dedicated to the early-stage researchers:

5. Field experiments design and statistics;
6. Scientific writing training;
7. Round-table breakout sessions ECR career development.

Table of Contents

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Keynote lecture - Claudia Kammann, Susanne Hamburge, Johannes Meyer zu Drewer, Nikolas Hagemann: BIOCHAR AS A CDR TECHNOLOGY: WHERE DOES IT STAND AND CAN IT BE COMBINED WITH OTHER CDR METHODS?	2
Keynote lecture - Boris Đurđević, Irena Jug, Bojana Brozović, Danijel Jug: BIOCHAR AND LIME APPLICATION EFFECT ON SOIL ORGANIC CARBON CONTENT UNDER DIFFERENT TILLAGE SYSTEMS ON ACID SOIL: A 7-YEAR FIELD EXPERIMENT	4
Branko B. Kordić, Slobodanka B. Dragojević, Branislav D. Jović: APPLICATION OF SYNTHETIC SOIL IN FTIR SPECTROSCOPIC INVESTIGATION OF SOIL COMPOSITION	5
Betelhem Mekonnen, Burkhard Wilske, Bezabih Addisu, Abebe Nigussie, Konrad Siegfried, Shimelis Gizachew, Tigist Yimer, Bishri Mohammed, Milkias Ahmed, Tilahun Abera, Amsalu Nebiyu, Reta Worku, Alemayehu Regassa, Tilahun Firomsa, Abdurahman Husien, Gebeyanesh Worku, Amante Lema, Amsalu Tilahun, Kefyalew Assefa, Bayu Dume, Getachew Eshete, Annett Pollex: BIOCHAR-BASED FERTILIZERS INCREASE CROP YIELDS IN ACIDIC SOILS OF ETHIOPIA	6
Ryan Pearson, Arthur Gross, Tobias Bromm, Bruno Glaser: VERTICAL BIOCHAR TRANSPORT IN SOIL IN A LONG-TERM FIELD EXPERIMENT IN GERMANY	7
Houda Lamane, Latifa Mouhir, Rachid Moussadek, Bouamar Baghdad, Ali El Bilali: INTERPRETABLE MACHINE LEARNING FOR SUSPENDED SEDIMENT PREDICTION IN A SEMI-ARID WATERSHED: A HYBRID MODELING APPROACH	8
Keynote lecture - David Fangueiro: MANURE MANAGEMENT AT FARM SCALE: PROBLEM OR OPPORTUNITY?	10
Keynote lecture - David Fangueiro: SLURRY ACIDIFICATION AS SOLUTION FOR SEVERAL PROBLEMS	10
Keynote lecture - Zoran A. Galić: GREENHOUSE GASES (GHG) EMISSION FROM DIFFERENT LAND USE	11
Huijun Ye, Huiying Lin, Muhammed Mustapha Ibrahim, Leiru Chen, Yang Liu, Roland Bol, Enqing Hou: PHOSPHORUS ADDITION IMPACTS ON SOIL NITROGEN DYNAMICS IN A SUBTROPICAL PLANTATION	12
Alvaro F. García-Rodríguez, Otávio dos Anjos Leal, Heike Knicker, Nina Siebers, Miguel A. Rosales, Roland Bol: BIOCHAR AMENDMENT TO SOILS AS A TOOL TO PREVENT NUTRIENT LEACHING AND INCREASE N-USE EFFICIENCY IN LETTUCE PLANTS	13
Brian J. Young, Pedro F. Rizzo: EVALUATION OF AMENDMENT PROPERTIES, MINERALIZATION, AND EFFECTS IN SOIL AND CROPS	14
Emeliane Kiladze, Nana Bitsadze: THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT MULCHING TYPES ON THE MYCORRHIZATION OF BLUEBERRY ROOTS AND THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF BOTH ABOVEGROUND AND BELOWGROUND PARTS OF THE BLUEBERRY PLANT	15

Leah Eitelberg, Wulf Amelung, Elmarie Kotzé, Gert Ceroni, Chris du Preez, Kathlin Schweitzer, Michael Baumecker, Sara L. Bauke: IMPACT OF SUBSOIL MELIORATION AND LONG-TERM AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT ON WATER USE OF ARABLE CROPS	16
Karol Osipiuk, Patryk Oleszczuk: HOW MONOSACCHARIDE IMPREGNATION OF FEEDSTOCK AFFECTS NUTRIENT RELEASE FROM OBTAINED BIOCHAR?	17
Jayantifull Hoojon, Idhayachandhiran Ilampooranan: CROP RESIDUE AS AN ORGANIC AMENDMENT: MODELLING BENEFITS AND TRADE-OFFS	18
Keynote lecture - Helmut Gerber: CRUCIAL ASPECTS OF PHOSPHORUS RECOVERY FROM SEWAGE SLUDGE IN CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE	20
Keynote lecture - Marina Paneque: EFFECT OF THE CARBONIZATION PROCESS OF SEWAGE SLUDGE ON THE PROPERTIES OF THE CHARS AND THEIR POTENTIAL BENEFITS AS SOIL AMENDMENTS	24
Nataša Đurišić Mladenović, Snežana Maletić: HYDROTHERMAL CARBONIZATION AS A SUSTAINABLE SOLUTION: LINKING WASTE MANAGEMENT (SDG 12), CLEAN WATER (SDG 6), AND CLIMATE ACTION (SDG 13)	25
Monika Raczkiewicz, Patryk Oleszczuk: NANO-BIOCHAR FOR SUSTAINABLE REMEDIATION OF POTENTIALLY TOXIC ELEMENTS-CONTAMINATED SOILS: A FOCUS ON FOOD SAFETY AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY	26
Tahra Al-Rashdi, Mushtaque Ahmed, Alexandros Stefanakis: DEWATERING AND TREATMENT OF DOMESTIC SEWAGE SLUDGE USING CONSTRUCTED REED BED	27
Nina Đukanović, Tamara Apostolović, Jasmina Anojčić, Sanja Mutić, Tijana Marjanović Srebro, Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin: THE INFLUENCE OF PYROLYSIS TEMPERATURE ON THE PROPERTIES OF BIOCHAR DERIVED FROM WHEAT STRAW	29
Keynote lecture - Gabriel Sigmund: POTENTIAL AND LIMITATIONS OF SORBENT AMENDMENTS FOR INCREASED MICROPOLLUTANT REMOVAL IN THE SOIL PASSAGE	31
Keynote lecture - Thomas D. Bucheli: EMERGING CONTAMINANTS IN ORGANIC SOIL AMENDMENTS	32
Prudence W. Mhlophe, Jaime L. Toney, Adrian M. Bass, John W. Crawford: MODIFIED SPENT COFFEE GROUNDS AND BIOCHAR REMEDIATION OF HEAVY METAL-CONTAMINATED URBAN SOILS IN GLASGOW	33
Marinela M.C. Cvetanoska, Ivona I.S. Sofronievaska, Pece P.S. Sherovski, Milena M.S.K. Spasovska Kolevska, Jane J.B. Bogdanov, Jasmina J.P.S. Petreska Stanoeva, Marina M.S. Stefova: ORGANOCHLORINE PESTICIDES AND POLYCHLORINATED BIPHENYLS IN SOILS SURROUNDING A HEXACHLOROCYCLOHEXANE DUMP SITE	34
Marija Gadžimuradova: DISENTANGLING SOIL PARAMETER EFFECTS ON PESTICIDE FATE BY SIMULATING AMENDMENT-DRIVEN CHANGES	35
Sara Adeleh, Tabea Becker, Roland Bol, Sonja Herres Pawlis, Thomas Pütz: ENVIRONMENTAL BEHAVIOR AND FATE OF BIOPLASTICS IN SOILS	36
Tamara Apostolović, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Marko Šolić, Jelena Beljin, Lutz Weihermüller, Snežana Maletić: BIOCHAR-INDUCED CHANGES IN THE TRANSPORT MECHANISMS OF CHLORINATED PHENOLS IN ALLUVIAL SOIL SYSTEMS	37

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

Maia Batsatsashvili, Lea Dedden, Roland Bol, Tim Spieker, Gretchen Gettel, Inge Wiekenkamp, Karsten Kalbitz, Thomas Pütz: DEFORESTATION EFFECTS ON THE SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF C AND N IN THE SOILS OF A FORESTED HEADWATER CATCHMENT IN THE EIFEL, GERMANY	39
Jasmina Anojčić, Sanja Mutić, Nina Đukanović, Tamara Apostolović, Tajana Simetić, Tijana Marjanović Srebro, Jelena Beljin: BIOCHAR-BASED ELECTROCHEMICAL SENSORS FOR PESTICIDES DETECTION IN AQUATIC ENVIRONMENT	40
Zhenzhen Li, Nina Siebers, Roland Bol, Wulf Amelung, Haishui Yang: SOIL NUTRIENT AVAILABILITY AND AGGREGATE DYNAMICS UNDER DITCH-BURIED ORGANIC MATERIALS IN A WHEAT-BASED ROTATION SYSTEM	41
Kristina Kalkan, Sreten Terzić, Maja Arok, Andrijana Andrić, Predrag Lugonja, Liljana Šašić Zorić, Tijana Nikolić Lugonja: ESTABLISHING A SOIL HEALTH BASELINE FOR GREEN INFRASTRUCTURE: SAMPLING NATURAL AND SEMI-NATURAL AREAS IN AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPES	42
Nikolina N. Dizdar, Ranko R. Čabilovski, Snežana P. Jakšić, Stanko B. Milić, Milorad S. Živanov, Dunja P. Anđelić, Aleksandar Ž. Mihaljev: MACRONUTRIENT (NPK) CONTENT IN DIFFERENT TYPES OF ORGANIC FERTILIZERS	43
Sijja, Wang: FUTURES OF PLANT-SOIL NITROGEN CYCLING FEEDBACKS UNDER GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE – CRITICAL EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT USING THE LARGE-SCALE MESOCOSM RESEARCH FACILITY AGRASIM	44
Milorad S. Živanov, Srđan I. Šeremešić, Jovica R. Vasin, Stanko B. Milić, Bojan Đ. Vojnov, Nikolina N. Dizdar, Dunja P. Anđelić: INDUSTRIAL COMPOST - SOIL ENHANCER IN MAIZE PRODUCTION	45
Aleksandar Piperevski, Biljana Balabanova: SOIL HEALTH – AN EVIDENCE FOR THE BIOGEOCHEMICAL INDICATORS ON REGIONAL VS. GLOBAL SCALE	46
Žygimantas Kidikas, Rytis Skominas, Vilma Naujokienė: REGIONAL DIFFERENCES OF IPCC TIER 1 AND TIER 2 FACTORS IN LITHUANIAN CROPLANDS	47
Sanja Vasiljević, Tijana Marjanović Srebro, Maja Vujić, Jasmina Agbaba, Radivoj Tomić, Aleksandra Tubić: IMPACT OF pH ON THE EFFICIENCY OF COAGULATION IN REMOVING MICROPLASTICS AND TEXTILE FIBERS FROM WATER	48
Stefan R. Mijatović, Tamara B. Apostolović, Snežana P. Maletić, Srđan D. Rončević, Marijana M. Kragulj Isakovski, Nina S. Đukanović, Jelena M. Beljin: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF BIOCHAR APPLICATION	49
Irina Jevrosimov, Jessica Drozd, Michael Zumstein, Gabriel Sigmund, Thorsten Hüffer, Thilo Hofmann, Snežana Maletić: ENVIRONMENTAL FATE OF MELAMINE: BIOTRANSFORMATION IN SOIL SYSTEMS	50
Dunja P. Anđelić, Snežana P. Maletić, Snežana P. Jakšić, Stanko B. Milić, Milorad S. Živanov, Nikolina N. Dizdar, Aleksandar Ž. Mihaljev: THE CONTENT OF ORGANIC MATTER, ORGANIC CARBON AND C/N RATIO IN DIFFERENT TYPES OF ORGANIC FERTILIZERS	51
Milica Škorić, Vojislava Bursić, Sonja Gvozdenac: DETERMINATION OF GLYPHOSATE RESIDUES IN THE DTD CANAL IN NOVI SAD	52

Dušan Rakić, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Zita Šereš, Nataša Đurišić Mladenović: COMPARISON OF TWO METHODS FOR EXTRACTION CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM SOIL SAMPLES	53
Ivana Bajić, Snežana Maletić, Tijana Zeremski, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Nina Đukanović, Irina Jevrosimov, Stanko Milić: PHYTOREMEDIATION POTENTIAL OF ENERGY CROPS AND PGPR INOCULANTS FOR THE REMEDIATION OF CONTAMINATED SOILS	54
Nadežda Stojanov, Jelena Beljin, Snežana Maletić, Nina Đukanović, Tijana Zeremski: THE POTENTIAL OF FIELD CROPS FOR PHYTOEXTRACTON OF HEAVY METALS FROM DREDGED SEDIMENT	55
Nenad Grba, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Jelena Tanasić, Slavica Ražić: REMOVAL OF MANGANESE IONS FROM WATER USING MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES	56
Burcu Kiran, Selda Murat-Hocaoglu, Sebnem Aynur, Fatone F., Salas, S.P., Maletsky, Z., Piccinetti, L.: SMART4ENV PROJECT: ENHANCING THE SCIENTIFIC CAPACITY OF TUBITAK MAM IN THE FIELD OF SMART ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR CLIMATE CHANGE CHALLENGES	57
Biljana Balabanova, Trajče Stafilov, Robert Šajn: ADVANCED SPATIAL MODELING FOR METALS DISTRIBUTION DUE TO THE LONGTIME MINING ACTIVITIES	58
Sana Ullah, Karolina Barcauskaite: COMPOST RELIEVES METAL TOXICITY AND HEALTH RISKS AND ENDURES LETTUCE PLANTS IN METAL POLLUTED SOILS WITH DIFFERENT pH LEVELS	59

COMPARISON OF TWO METHODS FOR EXTRACTION CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM SOIL SAMPLES

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Contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) are unregulated, infrequently monitored synthetic or natural substances that have been shown or suspected of negatively impacting human and environmental health. CECs include many different classes of compounds, such as pharmaceutically active compounds (PhACs), personal care products, illicit drugs, hormones, pesticides in current usage, per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), micro- and nano-plastics, and many others. The fate of CECs in the environment depends on their physical and chemical properties and environmental conditions. Since surface water receives most wastewater discharges, its use for irrigation can further transport many CECs to agricultural soils. Because plants tend to uptake organic and inorganic substances from the soil, the presence of CECs in agricultural areas has raised concerns about their potential introduction into the food chain.

This study aims to compare the efficiency of the two most frequently used methods for CECs extraction from soil samples, so-called Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, and Safe (QuEChERS) and Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), also known as pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), on a selected CECs compound (PhACs, PFAS, and pesticides). Target analysis of CECs in soil extracts was performed using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry. The comparison was based on method validation parameters such as contaminants recovery, limits of quantification, and matrix effect. QuEChERS extraction has shown better extraction efficiency than ASE for most selected compounds, proving its importance for wide-range screening of soil contamination.

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